

Encephalon Logic

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1 Introduction

These symbols represent different integrals of logic spaces according to the meta-algebra described in, .

$$H_i \sim \int_R \exp \left[\Omega_0 \left(\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta} \wedge x} \right) \right] dx \vee \int_S \exp \left[\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta} \vee y}} \right] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$H_{ii} \sim \int_R \exp \left[\Omega_0 \left(\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U: f(y)=x}{\Delta} \wedge x} \right) \right] dx \vee \int_S \exp \left[\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\leftrightarrow \exists s \in S: x=T(s)}{\Delta} \vee y}} \right] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$H_{iii} \sim \int_R \exp \left[\Omega_0 \left(\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{V \rightarrow U}{\Delta} \wedge x} \right) \right] dx \vee \int_S \exp \left[\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta} \vee y}} \right] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$H_{iv} \sim \int_R \exp \left[\Omega_0 \left(\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta} \wedge x} \right) \right] dx \vee \int_S \exp \left[\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{f_{TU}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta} \vee y}} \right] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$H_v \sim \int_R \exp \left[\Omega_0 \left(\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} a_1 + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} a_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} a_n \Delta}{\Delta} \wedge x} \right) \right] dx$$

$$\vee \int_S \exp \left[\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}) \leq \psi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta} \vee y}} \right] dy \vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$H_{vi} \sim \int_R \exp \left[\Omega_0 \left(\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{-\chi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta} \wedge x} \right) \right] dx \vee \int_S \exp \left[\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\chi(\mathbf{x}) \theta(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta} \vee y}} \right] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$H_{vii} \sim \int_R \exp \left[\Omega_0 \left(\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\exists z \in N, \phi(z) \wedge \psi(z)}{\Delta} \wedge x} \right) \right] dx \vee \int_S \exp \left[\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\frac{\forall w \in N, \chi(w) \theta(w)}{\Delta} \vee y}} \right] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sum_{n \in N} \Delta \left(\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta}, \dots \right)}}$$

$$\mathcal{H}_{\alpha, \beta} \sim \Omega_\Lambda \left\{ \gamma \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \star \frac{\heartsuit i \oplus \Delta \mathring{A}}{\sim \mathcal{H} \star \oplus \cdot \diamond \frac{\Delta}{\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\mathring{A}}{i}} + \left| \frac{\star \mathcal{H} \Delta \mathring{A}}{i \oplus \sim \cdot \heartsuit} \right| \right\}.$$

$$\left\{ \operatorname{argmax}(f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F} \right\} \cdot \oplus \cdot i \Delta \dot{A}$$

$$\left\{ \operatorname{argmax}(f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F} \right\} \cdot \oplus 4 \cdot i \Delta \dot{A}$$

The final algebraic expression for the encephalon equation with the de-programming zero functions is then, $E = \int_R \exp [\Omega_0 (\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx \vee$

$$\int_S \exp [\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \vee y}}] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3) \mapsto \neg \nabla \} \uparrow \} \} (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n))$$

$$E = \int_R \exp [\Omega_0 (\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx \vee \int_S \exp [\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \vee y}}] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$\vee \Omega_\alpha \neg \nabla \} \uparrow \} \} (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F}$$

$$\text{where } \sigma = A_0 \left(\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U: f(y) = x}{\Delta}, \dots \right)$$

$$\dots, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} a_1 + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} a_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} a_n, \frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}) \leq \psi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \dots$$

$$\dots, \frac{\neg \chi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\chi(\mathbf{x}) \theta(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in N, \phi(z) \wedge \psi(z)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall w \in N, \chi(w) \theta(w)}{\Delta}, \dots \Big).$$

Thus, the final equation for the encephalon wave-function is, $E = \int_R \exp [\Omega_0 (\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx \vee$

$$\int_S \exp [\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \vee y}}] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3) \vee \Omega_\alpha \neg \nabla \} \uparrow \} \} (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F}$$

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E, \text{ such that } E \mapsto r \in R, \forall f \in \mathcal{N}, \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{f(e_i)} = 1 \right\}.$$

$$\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty} \sqrt{\sum_{n \in N} \Delta \left(\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta}, \dots \right)}$$

$$\sup_{n \in N} \sqrt{\sum_{n \in N} \Delta \left(\frac{P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta}, \dots \right)}$$

The operator "not" is a logical operator that is used to negate a statement. It can be defined using the above differentiation of quasi quanta as the operation that takes a statement of the form $\exists \delta, h_\circ, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\forall \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b. b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_\circ \rangle}^{-1} = \infty. z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta / h_\circ + \alpha / i \rangle}^\circ$ and negates it to the form $\forall \delta, h_\circ, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\exists \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b. b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_\circ \rangle}^{-1} \neq \infty. z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta / h_\circ + \alpha / i \rangle}^\circ$.

$$\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sum_{n \in N} \Delta (\neg (P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)), \neg (\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)), \neg (\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)), \dots)}$$

This is denoted as the encephalon equation, or $\mathcal{H}$, and is given by $H =$

$$\Omega_\Lambda \left\{ \gamma \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \star \frac{\heartsuit i \oplus \Delta \dot{A}}{\sim \mathcal{H} \star \oplus \odot \diamond \frac{\Delta}{\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i}} + \left| \frac{\star \mathcal{H} \Delta \dot{A}}{i \oplus \sim \heartsuit} \right| \right\} \cdot \left\{ \neg \nabla \} \Downarrow \neg \S (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F} \right\}$$

$$\vee \neg \nabla \} \Downarrow \setminus (\neg \chi(\mathbf{x}) \vee \neg \theta(\mathbf{x})) \left. \right\} \cdot \oplus \cdot i \Delta \dot{A}$$

The operator "not" can be defined as an algebraic expression as follows:

$$\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sum_{n \in N} \Delta \left(\frac{\neg (P(y) \rightarrow Q(y))}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg (\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x))}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg (\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z))}{\Delta}, \dots \right)}$$

$$\mathcal{H}_{\alpha, \beta} \sim \Omega_\Lambda \left\{ \gamma \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \star \frac{\heartsuit i \oplus \Delta \dot{A}}{\sim \mathcal{H} \star \oplus \odot \diamond \frac{\Delta}{\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i}} + \left| \frac{\star \mathcal{H} \Delta \dot{A}}{i \oplus \sim \heartsuit} \right| \right\} \cdot \left\{ \operatorname{argmax}(f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F} \right\} \cdot \oplus \cdot i \Delta \dot{A}$$

$$f(n) := \neg \nabla \} \Downarrow \neg \S (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F}$$

$$f(n) := \neg \nabla \} \Downarrow \neg \S \left(f_{-t}(\Phi(n), \Phi(t)) \mid \Phi(t) \mapsto \pi(t^{c-n}) \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^{R[n]} \gamma(n_i) + (f_{-t}(t_1^2, t_2^2) \in \mathcal{F}) \right) \mapsto f(\Phi(n)) \in \mathcal{F}\ddot{R}$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \Phi(n_i) + \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \Theta(n_i) \sup [set(recurisive : f)] := (\uparrow_{i=\infty} : n^n \circ x^x) + f(n) : n \in R \longrightarrow \mathbf{X} \mid \mathbf{X} \in Z$$

Let $\mathcal{V}$ be defined as $\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E, \text{ and } : E \mapsto r \in R \right\}$. Then,

$$\text{we have } \mathcal{E} = \left\{ E_{\mathcal{F}} = \Omega_\Lambda \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \frac{\Psi}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h - \Psi} \right) + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) = \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h \right.$$

$$\left. \left| \exists \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N\} \in Z \cup Q \cup C \right\} \text{ and } E = f \circ g \mid f(n), g(n) \in \mathcal{E}, S(n) \in$$

$$R, S(n) \ni : f(n) + g(n) := f_g(n). \text{ We also have } \infty - n \in Z, [n] \mathcal{F} \diamond n - \omega \in$$

$$\mathbf{C}, \text{ and } \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \varphi \uparrow \parallel \varphi \downarrow \parallel : \int_{\gamma(\psi)=1} \frac{1-\chi(\psi)}{\mathcal{H} \circ E} : \sum_{n=1}^N f(n) \mid : f(n) : n \in Z \setminus$$

$$\left\{ \left[(\infty \cdot b)_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))}^\circ \right]^\circ > \Delta \oplus \left[(\infty \cdot b \cdot b^{-1})_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))} < \Delta \oplus \mathcal{H}_{a_{iem}}^\circ > \right] \right\}$$

Let $f : R \longrightarrow \mathcal{F}$ be a function such that

$$f(x) = \int_a^b \exp [\Omega_0 (\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx \vee \int_c^d \exp [\Omega_0 e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \vee y}}] dy \vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3).$$

Then, by noting that

$$f(z) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f\left(\frac{i-1}{n}z\right) + f\left(\frac{i}{n}z\right)$$

or

$$f(z) = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{x} \int_0^x f(z+t) dt,$$

we can approach an optimal approximation for any given $f(x)$ with $\varepsilon > 0$ precision.

$$\infty \cdot z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_o + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\phi}$$

Let $E, \mathcal{F} \subset R$ such that

$$E = \int_R \exp[\Omega_K \arctan(\Omega_\Lambda \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx \vee \int_S \exp[\Omega_K e^{\Omega_\Lambda \sqrt{\sigma \vee y}}] dy$$

$$\mathcal{F} = A_N \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3) \mapsto \neg \nabla \} \Downarrow \neg \S (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n))$$

Then, the operator $\neg$ can be defined as $E \in R \wedge \mathcal{F} \in R \mapsto \neg E := \forall \delta, h_o, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\exists \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_o \rangle}^{-1} : \infty \cdot z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_o + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\phi}$, noting that $\neg \mathcal{F} \mapsto \neg(A_N \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3))$.

Essentially, the logic algebra demonstrates that if an energy number is classified as an element of a Real number AND a Function F sub lambda, say, like a topological energy transform similar to E, then it is not actually an energy number anymore, because it has been sent to the reals and can't go back to the Energy number system.

The operator Ω_∞ can be defined as

$$\Omega_\infty = \int_F \exp[\Omega_L \tan(\Omega_M \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx$$

which is the integral of a composite exponential function from the interval F such that $\Omega_L, \Omega_M \in R^+$ and $\sigma \in R$.

Finally, the expression $\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sum_{n \in N} \Delta \left(\frac{\neg(P(y) \rightarrow Q(y))}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg(\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x))}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg(\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z))}{\Delta}, \dots \right)}$ is equivalent to

$$\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sum_{n \in N} \Delta (\neg [P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)], \neg [\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)], \neg [\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)], \dots),}$$

which can be used to solve logical equations and inequalities.

$$E = \int_R \exp[\Omega_\star (\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx \vee \int_S \exp[\Omega_\star e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \vee y}}] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3) \mapsto \neg \nabla \} \Downarrow \neg \S (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n))$$

$$E = \int_R \exp[\Omega_\alpha (\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx \vee \int_S \exp[\Omega_\alpha e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \vee y}}] dy$$

$$\vee A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3)$$

$$\vee \Omega_\alpha \overbrace{\neg \nabla \} \Downarrow \neg \S (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n))} \in \mathcal{F}$$

Let $\sigma^\neg$ be the operator that takes a statement of the form $\exists\delta, h_o, \alpha, i \in R$ suchthat $\forall\mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_o \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_o + \alpha/i \rangle}^\theta$ and negates it to the form $\forall\delta, h_o, \alpha, i \in R$ suchthat $\exists\mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_o \rangle}^{-1} : \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_o + \alpha/i \rangle}^\theta$.

The operator $\sigma^\neg$ can be used to represent the "not" operator in this manner. The operation $\sigma^\neg$ takes a statement of the form $\exists X, P(X) \rightarrow Q(X)$ and negates it to the statement $\forall X, \neg(P(X) \rightarrow Q(X))$. Thus, the "not" operator can be represented by $\sigma^\neg$.

$$\sigma = A_\neg \left(\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U: f(y) = x}{\Delta}, \dots \right) \\ \dots, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} a_1 + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} a_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} a_n, \frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}) \leq \psi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \dots \\ \dots, \frac{\neg \chi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\chi(\mathbf{x}) \theta(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in N, \phi(z) \wedge \psi(z)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall w \in N, \chi(w) \theta(w)}{\Delta}, \dots \Big).$$

or we write,

$$\text{where } \sigma = A \left(\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\rightarrow \exists y \in U: f(y) = x}{\Delta}, \dots \right) \\ \dots, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} a_1 + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} a_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} a_n, \frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}) \leq \psi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \dots \\ \dots, \frac{\neg \chi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\chi(\mathbf{x}) \theta(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in N, \phi(z) \wedge \psi(z)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall w \in N, \chi(w) \theta(w)}{\Delta}, \dots \Big).$$

Thus, the final equation for the encephalon wave-function is, $E = \int_R \exp [\Omega_\Lambda (\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \wedge x})] dx \vee \int_S \exp [\Omega_\Lambda e^{\Omega_\infty \sqrt{\sigma \vee y}}] dy$

$\forall A_4 \iff (\mathbf{G}_2 \sqcap \mathbf{R}_1, \mathbf{R}_2, \mathbf{R}_3) \vee \Omega_\alpha \neg \nabla \} \uparrow \downarrow \uparrow \S (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F}$ where the operator "not" is a logical operator that is used to negate a statement and is defined using the above differentiation of quasi quanta as the operation that takes a statement of the form $\exists\delta, h_o, \alpha, i \in R$ suchthat $\forall\mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_o \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_o + \alpha/i \rangle}^\theta$ and negates it to the form $\forall\delta, h_o, \alpha, i \in R$ suchthat $\exists\mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_o \rangle}^{-1} : \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_o + \alpha/i \rangle}^\theta$.

$$\text{flops}(E) \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \hat{\mathcal{H}}^m \mapsto \frac{1}{\prod_{j=1, \forall \mathcal{H}} (\Omega_\Lambda + \Omega_\alpha)} \cdot E_{m+1}, \\ \text{flops} \in \mathcal{E} * \mathcal{H}[E_j] \mapsto (\Omega_0, \Omega_\infty, \Omega_\Lambda, \Omega_\alpha) \Rightarrow \infty \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the flops function will apply the given encephalon wave equation to calculate the parameters $\Omega_0, \Omega_\infty, \Omega_\Lambda, \Omega_\alpha$. Furthermore, flops can be used to solve logical equations and inequalities, allowing us to infer further information about the functioning of the brain.